

EFFICACY OF SOME LEAF EXTRACTS AND SYNTHETIC INSECTICIDES FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF LEPIDOPTEROUS PESTS OF COTTON AND THEIR NATURAL ENEMIES IN ZARIA, KADUNA STATE

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ABSTRACT

The field trial was conducted during 2022 cropping season at Samaru, Zaria to evaluate the efficacy of some leaf extracts (Bush mint *Hyptis suaveolens*, *Guiera senegalensis*, Gum tree *Eucalyptus globulus*) and synthetic insecticides (Chlorpyrifos, Cypermethrin, Cyper plus, Imidacloprid) against Lepidopterous pests of cotton and their natural enemies. The experiment was laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design with three replications. Five spray applications of cotton at square, flower bud initiation stage, boll forming stage and boll maturing stage. Observations were taken on mean insect pest population mortality; the number of bolls damaged, and undamaged and the weight of cotton lint produced were assessed. The results showed that a combination of *G. senegalensis* and *eucalyptus* leaf extracts and Cyper plus significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) reduced the infestation of the insect population and boll damage. Cotton seed lint weight was significantly higher ($p \leq 0.05$) in both plots treated with combinations of plant extracts and synthetic insecticides compared with untreated plots. Cypermethrin, Cyper plus, Imidacloprid, and combination of botanical insecticides gave the overall best result compared with single application of *Hyptis* and *Eucalyptus* extracts. Therefore, combination of *G. senegalensis* and *eucalyptus* leaf extracts could be adopted as an alternative to synthetic insecticides for optimum cotton production in the study area.

Keywords: Insecticides, Leaf extract, *Lepidopterous*, *Natural Enemies*.

INTRODUCTION

Cotton, *Gossypium hirsutum* L., belongs to the family Malvaceae (Paterson, 2009 and is known as silver fibre due to its worldwide economic importance and this crop is attacked by 145 insect pest species Shah *et al.*, 2013). It is an important crop, which is cultivated in more than 80 countries of the world (Kutama *et al.*, 2015). In Nigeria, cotton is the fifth most important export crop after cocoa, groundnut, oil palm, rubber and one of the major sources of foreign exchange for the country (Kutama *et al.*, 2015).

However, among the major constraints hindering cotton cultivation are diseases and insect pests.

The cotton bollworm (*Helicoverpa armigera* Hubn), the spiny bollworms (*Earias insulana* Boisd and *E. biplaga* Wlk.), and the leafroller (*Sylepta derogata* F.) are major lepidopterous pests of cotton in Nigeria (Amatobi, 2007). These insect pests are currently being controlled by the application of wide range insecticides such as Organochlorines, Organophosphates and Pyrethroids (Shah *et al.*, 2013). Considering the hazardous effects of synthetic insecticides on non-target organisms including man and the environment (Rafiq *et al.*, 2014), synthetic insecticides are the most effective control tactic especially when the pests have exceeded the economic injury level (Oyewale 2014). Therefore, the need for

suitable and effective alternatives for the management of these pests is in demand. On the other hand, botanical insecticides are active against many lepidopterous species and have no adverse effects on natural enemies of target pests (Fadare and Amusa, 2003). The lepidopterous natural enemies include parasites (Syrphids, Tachnids, Braconids) and predators (Coccinelids, Forficulids, Pentatomids and Reduviids) (Amatobi, 2007). A better understanding of Integrated Pests Management (IPM) strategy based on selective materials would allow the survival of beneficial organisms and reduced pest populations that are destructive to the cotton plant. Therefore the present research was undertaken to evaluate the efficacy of three botanical leaf extracts and four synthetic insecticides on cotton bollworms and their natural enemies in the study area.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Glyphosate non-selective herbicides (4 litres /ha) were sprayed before ploughing. The fields were disc harrowed and ridged, followed by application of a mixture of Paraquat and Butachlor at the rate of 2 litres /ha two days after sowing to control the weeds. SAMCOT-9 variety is an erect, hairy and medium staple plant cultivated commercially. The variety is adapted to the North-West cotton growing zones of Nigeria under rain-fed conditions. The plant is reddish, with lobed leaves and slightly conical bolls which normally opened. The maturity period is between 130-150 days with a potential yield of 1500-2000 Kg/ha. It has a fibre length of 28-30 mm producing fine lint with good lustre. It is tolerant to bacterial blight disease.

The area marked out for the experiment consisted of twelve plots replicated four times with a gross size of 11.25 m² and a spacing of 1.5 m wider border margin and 1.0 m spacing between the plots. The experiment was laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD). Seed materials for the trial were obtained from the Cotton Research Programme

of the Institute for Agricultural Research (IAR) and were dressed with Apron star 8 g/kg before sowing. Four seeds were sown per hole on 90 cm spacing and 40 cm intra-row spacing. Emerged seedlings were thinned to two plants per stand at 3 weeks after sowing. Manual weeding was done at 3-weeks intervals beginning from four weeks after sowing to ensure weed-free crops. Fertilizer was applied at the recommended rate of 60: 25: 25 Kg/ha using NPK 20:10:10 at 3 WAS by side dressing at about 5 cm away from the base of the plant, and Urea (46 %) was applied as top dressing at 8 WAS.

The treatments consisted of three botanicals (Bush mint *Hyptis suaveolens*, *Guiera senegalensis*, and Gum tree *Eucalyptus globulus*), their combinations, Synthetic insecticides (Chlorpyrifos at 240 g a.i. /ha, Cyper plus 250 g a.i. /ha, Cypermethrin 720 g a.i. /ha, and Imidacloprid 250 g a.i. /ha, each in 225 litres of water/ha) water and unsprayed plots. The leaves of each test plant were pounded separately into a paste. Five hundred grams (500 g) paste of each plant leaf was weighed and added to 100 mls sterile clean hot water in a 500 mls conical flask and mixed properly using a glass sterile. The mixture was allowed to stand for 24 hours before sieving through a sterile clean muslin cloth. Liquid soap at 0.1 % was added to the filtrate as an emulsifier. The treatments were applied to the plants using a 16-litre Knapsack sprayer.

Post-spray counts of bollworms damage were recorded on five randomly selected plants from top, middle and bottom cotton plants at two-week intervals. Post-spray populations of natural enemies (parasites and predators) were carried out with an aerial net. The inner two rows of each 5 m by 5 m plot were used for the estimates of seed cotton yield. Data collected were subjected to statistical analysis using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) (SAS, 2003) and means were separated using Students Newmans Keuls (SNK) ($P \leq 0.05$).

RESULTS

Effect of Botanical Extracts and Synthetic Insecticides on mean Populations of Bollworms at different weeks after sowing in 2022 Cropping Season at Samaru

The result of the effect of botanical extracts and synthetic insecticides on population of bollworms showed that at 14 WAS, *Hyptis* leaf extract, unsprayed plots had significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) higher mean populations of

bollworms when compared to plots sprayed with *G. senegalensis* leaf extracts but no significant differences were recorded among other treatments. At 16 and 18 WAS, unsprayed plots, water and *Hyptis* leaf extracts supported significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) similar populations when compared with *eucalyptus* leaf extracts which were statistically at par with combinations of leaf extracts and synthetic insecticides (Table 1). The same was observed at 20 WAS.

Table 1: Effect of Botanical Extracts and Synthetic Insecticides on Mean Populations of Bollworms at different Weeks after Sowing in 2022 Cropping Seasons at Samaru

	Weeks after Sowing				
	12	14	16	18	20
<i>Hyptis</i>	6.00a	9.00a	10.25abc	8.25a	5.25a
<i>Senegalensis</i>	3.75bc	3.75cd	4.25cde	4.25bcd	0.50c
<i>Eucalyptus</i>	1.25cd	1.00d	8.500abcd	7.00abc	4.50ab
<i>Hyptis</i> +	2.00cd	5.50bc	0.50e	3.75cd	2.75bc
<i>Senega</i> <i>Hyptis</i> +	2.25cd	6.00bc	3.25cde	2.00d	2.00bc
<i>Eucaly</i> <i>Senegalen</i> +	1.25cd	3.50cd	7.25cde	3.25cd	2.00bc
<i>Eucalyptus</i>					
Chlorpyrifos	2.75cd	3.50cd	1.75de	1.75d	2.00bc
Cypermethrin	2.00cd	3.50cd	4.25cde	3.50cd	0.75c
Cyper Plus	1.00d	1.25d	3.25cde	1.75d	0.50c
Imidacloprid	0.50d	2.25d	3.25cde	0.500d	0.50c
Water	5.00ab	8.00ab	13.75ab	7.75ab	5.75a
Unsprayed	6.25a	7.75ab	14.75a	9.25a	5.75a
Mean	2.83	4.58	6.25	4.42	2.69
SE±	0.59	0.74	1.70	1.02	0.64

Means within the same column followed by the different letter(s) are significantly different at ($P=0.05$) of the Student Newman Keuls (SNK) Test

WAS: Weeks after Sowing

Effect of Botanical Extracts and Synthetic Insecticides on Number of Undamaged Bolls, Damaged Bolls, and the Weight of Lint kg/ha, in 2022 Cropping Seasons at Samaru

There were significant differences ($P \leq 0.05$)

among the botanical extracts and synthetic insecticides in the mean number of undamaged bolls as shown in (Table 2). Combinations of *Hyptis* and *Eucalyptus*, Cyper plus and Imidacloprid had more ($P \leq 0.05$) number of undamaged bolls compared to other treatments

but was statistically similar to all the botanical extracts except the *Hyptis* leaf extracts, water and untreated control. The lowest mean number of undamaged bolls was recorded on plots sprayed with *Hyptis*, water and unsprayed plots. On the number of bolls damaged, there was a significant difference ($P \leq 0.05$) among the treatments. *Hyptis* leaf extracts and unsprayed plots had significantly higher mean number of damaged bolls compared with untreated control. However, there were no statistical differences among synthetic insecticides on the weight of

undamaged lint. Similarly, there was no significant difference between applications of the leaf extracts singly or in combination on the weight of damaged lint. Number of damaged lint was significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) higher on plots sprayed with *Hyptis* leaf extract, water and untreated plots but not statistically different from *G. senegalensis*, *Eucalyptus* and a combination of *Hyptis* and *Eucalyptus* extracts. The least weight of damaged lint was recorded from plots sprayed with all the synthetic insecticides.

Table 2: Effect of Botanical Extracts and Synthetic Insecticides on the Number of Undamaged Bolls, Damaged Bolls, Weight of Undamaged Lint, and Damaged Lint kg/ha, in 2022 Cropping Seasons at Samaru

Treatments	Number of undamaged bolls	Number of damaged bolls	Weight of undamaged lint kg/ha	Weight-damaged lint kg/ha
<i>Hyptis</i>	7.75c	12.75a	138.89cd	583.33a
<i>Senegalensis</i>	14.5ab	8.00bc	167.11cd	416.67abc
<i>Eucalyptus</i>	16.00ab	8.75bc	291.67cd	541.68ab
<i>Hyptis</i> + <i>Senega</i>	14.50ab	9.50bc	250.00cd	527.78ab
<i>Hyptis</i> + <i>Eucal</i>	19.25a	10.00bc	361.11bc	305.56bcd
<i>Senegalen</i> + <i>Eucaly</i>	11.75abc	11.75bc	388.89abc	250.00cd
Chlorpyrifos	12.75abc	10.50bc	375.00abc	430.56abc
Cypermethrin	16.00ab	11.75bc	541.67ab	111.11d
Cyper Plus	18.50a	4.00c	541.92ab	166.67d
Imidachloprid	20.50a	4.75c	597.23a	125.25d
Water	4.50c	20.75a	111.11d	680.56a
Unsprayed	5.25c	15.75ab	138.89cd	527.78ab
Mean	13.44	10.62	325.29	388.91
SE±	3.14	3.19	54.74	62.24

Means within the same column followed by the different letter(s) are significantly different at ($P=0.05$) of the Student Newman Keuls (SNK) Test

WAS: Weeks after Sowing

Effect of Botanical Extracts and Synthetic Insecticides on Mean Populations of Predators at a Weeks after Sowing in 2022 Cropping Seasons at Samaru

There was no significant difference recorded among the botanical extracts and synthetic insecticides on mean population of predators at 12 WAS as shown in (Table 3). However, at 14 WAS, *Eucalyptus*, water, unsprayed plots and the combinations of *Hyptis* and *G. senegalensis*, *Hyptis* and *Eucalyptus* leaf extract significantly recorded a higher mean of

predators which were at par compared to all synthetic insecticides. At 16 WAS *Hyptis*, *G. senegalensis* leaf extracts significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) had a higher mean population of predators but no significant difference was recorded among other treatments. *A* leaf extract at 18 WAS a significantly recorded with a higher ($P \leq 0.05$) mean predator population but no significant difference recorded among the botanical and synthetic insecticides on the mean population of predators at 20 WAS.

Table 3: Effect of Botanical Extracts and Synthetic Insecticides on Mean Populations of Predators at different Weeks after Sowing in 2022 Cropping Seasons at Samaru

	Weeks after Sowing				
	13	14	16	18	20
<i>Hyptis</i>	0.50	0.75b	2.25a	4.50b	7.00
<i>Senegalensis</i>	1.00	1.50b	5.75a	3.50b	2.75
<i>Eucalyptus</i>	0.25	6.00a	1.50b	10.00a	8.50
<i>Hyptis</i> +	1.25	4.25ab	1.25b	0.75b	4.00
<i>Senega</i>					
<i>Hyptis</i> + <i>Eucal</i>	1.25	4.50ab	0.25b	0.50b	1.75
<i>Senegalen</i> +	2.50	1.00b	0.75b	0.00b	7.50
<i>Eucalyptus</i>					
Chlorpyripos	2.70	3.50ab	1.00b	1.00b	9.50
Cypermethrin	1.25	1.00b	0.75b	1.00b	4.25
Cyper Plus	0.50	1.25b	3.00ab	0.50b	5.75
Imidachloprid	1.25	1.25b	1.25b	3.25b	4.25
Water	0.75	5.50a	4.50a	3.00b	1.00
Unsprayed	0.25	6.50a	3.00ab	4.00b	6.25
Mean	1.13	3.08	2.35	2.67	6.18
SE±	0.74	0.85	0.76	1.48	2.03

Means within the same column followed by the different letter(s) are significantly different at (P=0.05) of the Student Newman Keuls (SNK) Test

WAS: Weeks after Sowing

DISCUSSION

The present study shows the insecticidal action of some tested plant extracts to the synthetic insecticides for the management of lepidopterous pests. These results are in concordance with the observations of Li *et al.* (2006), who found that more than 60 % of boll was damaged by *H. armigera* compared with untreated controls. The combination of *G. senegalensis* and *Eucalyptus* leaf extracts warrants more attention because of the reduction it caused in the numbers of lepidopteran larvae comparable to Cyper plus. These results showed the potential of leaf extract to reduce pest populations, and environmentally friendly pesticides in organic and commercial agriculture. Biopesticides have been reported to effectively reduce the larval population of lepidopterous pests (Malinga and Laing, 2022)).

The results on yield showed that a significantly higher yield of seed cotton was recorded on the combination of *G. Senegalensis* and *Eucalyptus* leaf extracts and Cyper plus, followed by imidacloprid and *Eucalyptus* leaf extract. This is contrary to the findings of Kumar and Stanley (2010), who reported that although lambda-cyhalothrin enhanced seed cotton yields, it caused mortality in both destructive and useful insect species. The parasites and predators recovered from the botanical, synthetic insecticides and control plots were similar. Botanical insecticides may allow the survival of the beneficial species but the mortality of the destructive ones. On the other hand, synthetic insecticides reduced the population of both the beneficial and destructive species of insects (Fadare and Amusa 2003). The parasites recovered from the

trial plots included Tachnids and braconids while the predators included Coccinellids, Pentatomids and Reduviids as listed in an earlier report (Fadare and Amusa 2003). Botanical insecticides, being highly selective conserve the populations of parasites and predators as well as other beneficial species while they suppress Lepidopterous populations for which they are specific. Bull *et al.* (1979) reported a deliberate suppression of beneficial species populations with methyl parathion and subsequent rapid increases in the outbreak of *Heliothis* sp. on cotton fields. However synthetic insecticides may have adverse effects on parasites and predators in the agro-ecosystem. The seed cotton yields of plants sprayed with botanical and synthetic insecticides were higher than that of the untreated control. The lowest number of damaged bolls was observed in plots that were treated with a combination of *G. senegalensis* and *Eucalyptus* leaf extracts and Cyper Plus. The effects of *G. senegalensis*, *Eucalyptus* leaf extracts, Imidachloprid and cyper plus on the reduction in boll corresponded with the reduction in the numbers of Lepidoptera on the plots where these treatments were applied. The high yields could be attributed to the effective control of the foliage pests and bollworms which consequently enhanced the quantity and quality of the cotton lint. Damaged lint was higher on plots sprayed with *Hyptis*, *G. senegalensis*, *Eucalyptus* and unsprayed plots; the least number of damaged lint was recorded from plots sprayed with synthetic insecticides. Similar trends of results were observed by Nawaz *et al.* (2019) and Ali *et al.* (2022) on the effectiveness of imidacloprid against cotton aphids. Many pest species are affected by Imidacloprid just because of the dual mode of action, such as contact, and systemic effects. Yi *et al.* (2012) experimented to determine the efficacy of Imidacloprid and observed 100 % aphids' mortality.

The results show that the effectiveness of Cyper Plus may significantly reduce the population build-up of bollworms over time. All combined botanical leaf plots performed excellently as compared to synthetic insecticide-applied plots. Despite the negative effect of synthetic insecticide on the Populations of natural enemies (Sharma *et al.*, 2008), beneficial insects were significantly higher in the plots treated with botanical extracts at both vegetative and boll formation stages of the cotton. The decrease of the natural enemies in synthetic plots shows that this strategy is harmful to natural enemies, while the botanical extracts safeguard natural enemies (Mancini *et al.*, 2008; Hohmann *et al.*, 2010).

CONCLUSION

Results of the experiment obtained in this study revealed that all the plant extracts have potential value to substitute synthetic insecticides on lepidopteran pests since they are environmentally friendly and less toxic to natural enemies as compared to other synthetic pesticides. Imidacloprid, Cyper plus and cypermethrin gave the best result which was compared to an application of *hyptis* leaf extracts. Therefore combination of *G. senegalensis* and *eucalyptus* leaf extracts could be adopted as an alternative to synthetic insecticides for optimum cotton production in the study area.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Cotton Research Programme, Institute for Agricultural Research (IAR), ABU Zaria for technical and financial assistant. Mr Elias Otokpa and Muhammad Saleh for field assistance.

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